

Empirical Study On the Relationship Between Government Expenditures and Nigerian Gross Domestic Products (1999 – 2022)

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Abstract - This study examines relationship between government expenditures and the Nigerian Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from 1999 to 2022. The data for this study were obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Multiple Linear Regression model was adopted for the study to determine the relationship between the GDP, government final consumption expenditure, government private consumption expenditure and indirect taxes and the result showed that there is a significant relationship with the p-value (0.005). The result also shows with Ordinary Least Square(OLS) method that significant relationship exists between Nigerian GDP, Government final consumption expenditure and Government private consumption expenditure while indirect taxes has no relationship with the Nigerian GDP for the years of study. The result of multiple coefficient of determination for this study is 98.64 percent which indicates that government final consumption, government private consumption and indirect taxes expenditures accounted for about 98.6 percent of the total variation in the GDP for the period of study.

Keywords - Government Final Consumption Expenditure, Government Private Consumption Expenditure, Indirect Taxes, Gross Domestic Products (GDP), Multiple Linear Regression (MLR).

I. INTRODUCTION

Although, there have been a substantial number of studies on the relationship between public expenditures and economic growth both in Nigeria and other countries, the subject is still relevant in developed and developing countries. The general perception is that, public expenditure especially public investment expenditure should stimulate economic growth. This view has been buttressed by (Barro 1990). According to Barro (1990), government investment expenditures are more likely to contribute positively to real economic growth whereas government consumption expenditure should impact negatively on economic growth. For empirical analysis, it is often difficult to categorize government expenditure. Some activities that are considered as investment expenditures by one institution might be considered as consumption expenditure by another. This makes categorization of government expenditure

strenuous. Government expenditure remains an important instrument utilized in the process of development. It plays a pivotal role in the functioning of any economy at almost all stages of growth and development. Most developing and developed countries today use public expenditure to improve income distribution, direct the allocation of resources in desired areas, and influence the composition of national income (Assi et al., 2019; Vtyurina, 2020; World Bank, 2008). In developing countries for instance, the variation in government spending prototype is not only projected to pledge stabilization but also to encourage economic growth and expand employment opportunities (World Bank, 2015).

As public expenditure in Nigeria continues to increase public debt, both theoretical and empirical economists have shown a great deal of interest in the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. Due to the lack of agreement on the findings and recommendations made, current

academic research have produced outcomes that have been more confusing than beneficial (Nyasha and Odhiambo (2019); Okpabi and Akiri, 2021). Yasin, (2000); Attari and Javed, (2013) are a few researchers that found a favourable influence, while Nurudeen and Usman, (2010) reported a detrimental impact. Additionally, several studies have concluded that public expenditure has little or no effect on economic expansion (see for example, Schaltegger and Torgler, (2007).

One cannot overstate the importance of comprehending the nature of the impact, if any, of government expenditure on economic growth in the current environment of low domestic and global economic growth rates, skyrocketing public debt, and borrowing by governments to increase expenditure to boost their economies. Economic expansion is a key macroeconomic goal because it makes it possible to raise living standards and create jobs. A rapidly increasing growth rate not only attracts attention from around the world but also prepares the road for development. Economic growth means an increase in a nation's potential for production.

It describes a rise in the volume of products and services produced in a nation through time. The most comprehensive gauge of economic expansion is the gross domestic product (GDP). It indicates the total market value of all commodities and services generated throughout an economy, typically one year. For developing nations in particular, the link between government expenditure and economic growth is crucial. The need to free themselves from the grip of extreme poverty and put themselves on the path of rapid progress is the reason behind this. To do this, governments in developing nations have started a variety of expenditure initiatives.

Unfortunately, economic theories do not always lead to conclusive findings about how government expenditure affects economic growth. It has caused a lot of debate among academics. Some academics contend that raising government expenditure will enhance output and help prevent economic downturns. For instance, in their many research on the relationship between government expenditure

and economic growth, Agbonkhese and Asekhome (2014), Akpan and Abang (2013), and Okoro (2013) all came to the same conclusion: Government expenditure has a positive and considerable impact on economic growth. A boost in government expenditure, particularly when it is financed by borrowing, may slow economic growth, according to some academics, see for example, Folster and Henrekson (2001), Egbetunde and Fasanya (2013) who hypothesized that there were no visible link between government expenditures and economic growth.

Over the years, the connection between public expenditures and economic expansion has remained dormant; expenditures on social and economic infrastructures, such as roads, telecommunication, schools, energy, and health, typically have a favourable effect on the country's output. However, in developing nations, an increase in government expenditures typically increases taxation or borrowing.

As a result, there will be less overall demand as per capita income and labour demand decline. By the end of 2019, Nigeria's national government had spent roughly 9.7 trillion dollars (Varrella, 2021). Because of factors including the expansion of the civil service and the disproportionate remuneration for political office holders, a sizeable part of the federal government's expenditure in Nigeria had gone toward recurrent costs over time. From 36.21 billion (or \$4.5 billion) in 1990 to almost 3.109 trillion (or \$20.68 billion) in 2010, recurring expenditures grew.

From 24.04 billion (approximately \$2.9 billion) in 1990 to 234.45 billion (about \$2.29 billion) in 2000, the total amount of capital expenditure climbed at a decreasing rate. As of 2010, capital expenditure totalled 883.87 billion (nearly \$5.88 billion). However, as of 2010, just recurrent expenses made up more than 75% of all government expenditures (CBN, 2017).

Nigeria's general government spent 18,672 billion LCU in total in 2020. Nigeria's general government total expenditure climbed by an average annual rate

of 12.97% from 2,510 billion LCU in 2001 to 18,672 billion LCU in 2020 (CBN, 2021). Interestingly, achieving a sustained economic growth is a macro-economic objective that every nation drives at achieving. Admittedly, Ijuo and Andohol (2020) observed that ensuring a quick and sustainable economic growth and development is a main goal of most economies of the world (to which developing countries, Nigeria to be specific is not left out in the search). In this view, Essien (1997) opined that economic growth is the most important objective of government in developing countries. Accordingly, government spending has formed a point of debate for achieving economic growth in public economics. This is important for developing countries like Nigeria, most of which have experienced increasing level of public expenditure over time.

This tends to be associated with rising fiscal deficits, resulting from inadequate system of expenditure control, intense competition for funds among various Ministries, Agencies and Departments (MDAs), suggesting their limited ability to raise sufficient revenue to finance higher levels of government expenditures (Kolawole, 2016). For instance, between 2010 and 2015 total government expenditure increased from ₦153.9 billion to ₦5.06 trillion while GDP continued to wobble between 4.9% in 2010 and 2.7% in 2015 with less than 1% in the first and second quarters of 2016.

In general, it is believed that Nigerian economic policies have had a big influence on the trend of government expenditures for economic growth. Economic theories do not automatically make strong conclusions about the relationship between government expenditures and the gross domestic products (GDP).

Almost every economist would agree that there are situations in which lower levels of government expenditures would improve economic growth and there are other circumstances where higher levels of government expenditures would be attractive (Liew 1985). However, the reality in Nigeria leads the policy makers to become divided as whether the expansion of government expenditures promotes or obstructs economic growth. In the meantime, in most of the

previous empirical studies, see for example, Abu and Abdullahi,(2010); Badamosi, (2003); Robinson et al., (2014); Onifade et al., (2020),Ebong, et al (2016), Oyinlola and Akinnibosun (2013), Olayungbo and Olayemi (2018), Idris and Bakar (2017), Ihugba and Njoku (2017), Chimobi (2016), Diyoke, et al (2017), Oluwanmi and Tajuden (2007), Abutu and Agbede (2015), Ukwueze (2015); Bonnwa and Ishmael (2017) and Gupta (2018)observed that no consensus evidence have existed for the relationship between government expenditures and GDP. Results and evidences vary by countries/regions, analytical methods employed, and categorization of public expenditures which therefore made significance the place of this study.

Therefore, this study would fill this gap, by examining the relationship of government expenditures Gross Domestic Products (GDP) in Nigeria between 1999 and 2022 in order to validate if public expenditures have positive relationship on the Nigerian Gross Domestic Products or not.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Description

The data is secondary source and were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The population includes the indices of GDP, Government consumption expenditure, Government private expenditure and indirect taxes. The sample comprised their indices from 1999 to 2022.

Method of Data Analysis

This analysis would be subjected to a multiple linear regression to ascertain the relationship of government expenditures, to GDP. This test known as an Ordinary Least Squares Method (OLS) would be used to test whether there is existence of any significant relationship between GDP and the independent variables (Government consumption expenditure, Government private consumption expenditure and Indirect taxes).

The Model Specification

The model for this study is specified on the general form as

$$GDP = f(GC, PC, IT)$$

Equation (1) can also be explained as

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GC + \beta_2 PC + \beta_3 IT + \mu_i$$

where,

is the Gross Domestic product (dependent variable)
is the Government Consumption Expenditure (independent variable)

is the Private consumption (independent variable)
is the Government indirect taxes (independent variable)

Equation (2) could be used to explain the relationship between explanatory (independent) variables and the GDP and could be transformed mathematically to as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \beta_3 X_{i3} + \mu_i, i = 1, 2, 3$$

where:

μ_i is the error term associated with the model

Equation (3) could be simplified in a matrix form as

$$Y_i = X_i \beta_i + \mu_i$$

where,

$$Y_i = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{bmatrix}, X_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1k} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2k} \\ x_{31} & x_{32} & \dots & x_{3k} \end{bmatrix}, \beta_i = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \end{bmatrix}, \mu_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{i1} \\ \mu_{i2} \\ \mu_{i3} \end{bmatrix}$$

In the above matrix formulation, the elements of X and Y are in deviation forms where X matrix no longer contains the column for constant.

Minimizing the error term and transposing it, the result yields

$$\text{Min}(\mu^T \mu) = (y - Xb)^T (y - Xb)$$

Expanding Equation (5) and taking the partial derivative with respect to β , then the result yields

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mu^T \mu}{\partial \beta} \right) = -2(x^T x) + 2(x^T y) = 0$$

$$\hat{b} = (x^T x)^{-1} x^T y$$

Similarly, the constant (b_0) would be obtained as

$$\hat{b}_0 = \bar{y} - \hat{b}_i \bar{X}_i$$

Test of Significance

This test would be to ascertain the significant relationship (if any) of each of the Government Expenditures on Gross Domestic Product (GDP). After the estimation of the model parameters; the model would be tested for their sufficiency and statistical reliability. In this study, the t-statistic would be used.

The null and alternative hypotheses for the test are given as:

$$H_0 : b_i = 0$$

$$H_1 : b_i \neq 0, \text{ for at least one } \beta_i^s, i = 1, 2, 3$$

and the test statistic is given by

$$t_i = \frac{b_i}{SE(b_i)}$$

where,

$$SE(b_i) = \sqrt{\text{Var}(b_i)}$$

With its critical value given as degrees of freedom and the null hypothesis would be rejected if , otherwise accept .

Coefficient of Multiple Determination (R2)

A measure of the goodness of fit is the square of the correlation coefficient, R2 that shows the percentage of the total variation in the dependent variable that can be explained for by the independent variable. In this study, it would be used to determine the percentage of the total variation in the dependent variable (GDP) that is explained by the independent variables (Government expenditures). The Coefficient of Multiple Determinations (R2) is given by

$$R^2 = \frac{SS_R}{SS_T} = 1 - \frac{ESS}{TSS}$$

Results and Discussions

Graphical Presentation of GDP and Government Expenditures

From Figure 1 we observed that there is no relationship between the gross domestic product and government expenditures which include government final consumption expenditure, government private consumption expenditure and indirect taxes over the years of this research. This means that significant gap between GDP and the government expenditures over the years of study.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics: GDP (Y), Govt final Consumption, Govt. Private Consumption (X2), and Indirect Taxes(X3)

	N	SE Mean	Median	Mean	Std. Deviation
GDP	24	11683	58796	70754	57236
Govt. Final Consumption	24	716	4946	4434	3506
Govt. Private Consumption	24	719	1190	1086	878
Indirect Taxes	24	85.0	380.4	539.4	416.5

From the output of the descriptive statistics, it showed that government final consumption expenditure has the highest mean and standard deviation of 4434 and 3506 respectively followed by Government private consumption expenditure with the mean of 1086 and standard deviation 878 while that of indirect taxes has the least mean and standard deviation of 539.4 and 416.5 respectively This means that if compared with mean relationship to the GDP both government final consumption and government private consumption

expenditures have more relationship to GDP than indirect taxes over the years of study.

Multiple Regression Analysis (OLS) of GDP versus Government Final Consumption Expenditure, Government Private Consumption Expenditure and Indirect Taxes

The Estimated Multiple Regression Model is obtained as:
 $GDP = - 5770 + 16.5 GC - 55.6 PC + 118 IT$

Table 2 Analysis of Variance Table for Multiple Regression Analysis

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Regression	3	74321102540	24773700847	482.60	0.000
Residual Error	20	1026679702	51333985		
Total	23	75347782242			

The Test

$H_0 : \alpha_i = 0$ (There is no Significant Relationship)

$H_1 : \alpha_i \neq 0$ (There is significant Relationship)

$\alpha = 0.05$

Decision Rule: Reject the Null hypothesis if $F_{obs} > F_{crit}$, otherwise accept the null hypothesis.

Discussion of Result: From the ANOVA Table, the P-Value in the regression model is (0.00) which is less than P-value (0.005) indicates that the model

estimated by the regression procedure is significant at level of 0.05 which revealed that at least one coefficient is different from zero. The result shows that government final consumption expenditure, government private consumption expenditure and indirect taxes are significant. Therefore, we reject the null that there is no relationship between GDP and the selected government expenditures.

Statistical Test of Significance of Estimated Parameters (t-Statistic)

The test would be carried out to check for the significance relationship between each of the variables and GDP. Statistically, the t-statistic of the variable under consideration would be interpreted based on the following statements of hypotheses:

$H_0 : \beta_1 = 0$ (There is no relationship between GDP and Govt. final consumption)

$H_0 : \beta_2 = 0$ (There is no relationship between GDP and Govt. private consumption)

$H_0 : \beta_3 = 0$ (There is no relationship between GDP and Indirect taxes)

Decision Rule: If the calculated value of t is greater than the tabulated value, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the various government expenditures and GDP over the years of study, otherwise, accept the null hypothesis at level of significance.

Table 3 Summary Result of the test of Significance

Term	Coefficients					Remark
	Coeffi	SE Coeff	T	P	Decision	
Constant	-5770.10	2616.66	-2.2051	0.039		
Govt.Final Consumption	16.53	6.59	2.5078	0.021	Reject	Relationship exist
Govt.privateConsumption	-55.63	27.71	-2.0075	0.058	Accept	No Relationship
Indirect taxes	118.01	8.22	14.3488	0.000	Reject	Relationship exist

From Table 3, we can deduce that government final consumption expenditure and indirect taxes are statistically significant while government private consumption expenditure is statistically insignificant. This implies that government final consumption expenditure and indirect taxes have significant relationships with GDP while government private consumption expenditure has no significant relationship that exists with GDP over the period of study.

The Coefficient of Determination R² Summary of Model

S = 7164.77 R-Sq = 98.64% R-Sq(adj) = 98.43%

PRESS = 2204432994 R-Sq(pred) = 97.07%

The R² (0.9864) is a goodness of fit test which shows the amount of the variation in the dependent

variables (GDP) that are explained by government final consumption, government private consumption and indirect taxes expenditures. The value of the R² for this study is 98.64% indicating that government final consumption, government private consumption and indirect taxes expenditures account for about 98.64% of the variation in the GDP.

III. CONCLUSION

In an effort to investigate the relationship that exist between government expenditures and Nigeria GDP for the period of 1999 to 2022 using Multiple Linear Regression Analysis, the empirical evidence from the study had shown that government expenditures have 98.64% significant influence on the gross domestic product (GDP) of Nigeria between 1999 and 2022. However, government final consumption and indirect taxes have significant relationship while

there is no existence of relationship between government private consumption and Nigeria Gross Domestic product over the period of study. In line with the empirical findings of this study, hence, the following recommendations were made:

- Government should shift its focus from consumption related activities to investment activities like expenditures on infrastructural development.
- Government should critically evaluate components of its investments expenditures to efficiently allocate its scarce resources towards projects that are worthwhile.
- Government should strengthen and improve its domestic revenue mobilization to finance its expenditures
- To enhance real economic growth in Nigeria, sustainable public expenditure management practices must be adopted. Proper measures of costs and benefits should be implemented to ensure financial feasibility and there should be clear criteria for allocating resources to promote transparency.

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